

READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS AND WORD PROBLEM PERFORMANCE OF BSED-MATHEMATICS MAJOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13785026>

ABSTRACT

Reading comprehension skills are crucial in understanding and interpreting written information, particularly in mathematics. Reading comprehension and word problems are two critical components of a solid educational foundation. However, mathematics students often face challenges in reading comprehension that affect their performance in solving word problems. This study investigated the relationship between reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of BSED-mathematics majors. Pure-quantitative design, specifically a Descriptive-Correlational method and Total Enumeration Sampling Technique was utilized to gather data from the respondents. Researchers also used Pearson r-correlation as a research tool to determine the relationship between the two variables. The result implied that null hypothesis was rejected. As the study revealed, the researchers conclude that there is significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of the BSED- mathematics majors where the reading comprehension skills affected the word problem performance of the mathematics students. This study recommends for future researchers to further analyze the effect of Reading Comprehension in the mathematical skills of the students.

Keywords: *Inferential Comprehension, Evaluative Comprehension, Accuracy in Solving Problem, Speed in Problem-solving*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Reading comprehension skills are crucial in understanding and interpreting written information, particularly mathematics. Reading comprehension and word problems are two critical components of a solid educational foundation. However, mathematics students often face challenges in reading comprehension that affect their performance in solving word problems.

Vilenius et al., (2008) showed the relationship between reading comprehension and mathematical word problem-solving. In Kosova, the study of Kurshumlia R. and Vula E. (2019) revealed that using reading comprehension strategies impacts reading comprehension and has a positive answer, improving students' skills in mathematical word problem-solving. The reading comprehension strategies enabled students to have a more precise meaning and understanding of the word problems.

In the Philippines, on the other hand, Costas's (2017) study revealed a significant relationship between the level of reading comprehension skills and numeracy performance. The study of Nicolas and Emata (2018) revealed that using an integrative approach through reading comprehension is more effective in enhancing students' problem-solving skills, particularly in ordering/integrating and critical thinking, than using conventional methods.

In South Central Mindanao, the study of Ronquillo and Ngag (2023), revealed that students' reading skills, specifically their comprehension skills significantly affect their academic performance in English. However, it was not discussed in the study the correlation between the students' reading comprehension skills, and their word problem performance in Mathematics.

Indeed, reading comprehension is crucial in problem-solving. It involves understanding and extracting meaning from written information. Hence, this study aimed to determine the significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of BSED-mathematics majors for the school year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine how reading comprehension skills affect the word-problem performance of BSED Mathematics majors.

This research specifically aimed to respond to the following questions;

1. What is the level of reading comprehension skills of the BSED-mathematics major, in terms of:

- 1.1 Inferential Comprehension; and
 - 1.2 Evaluative Comprehension?
 2. What is the level of word problem performance of BSED-Mathematics major, in terms of:
 - 2.1 Accuracy in solving the problem; and
 - 2.2 Speed in problem-solving?
 3. Is there any significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of BSED-Mathematics major?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study was quantitative in nature, namely a descriptive-correlational to analyze the relationship between reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of BSED-mathematics major at Senator Ninoy Aquino College Foundation, Senator Ninoy Aquino, Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2023-2024.

According to Bhandari (2021), A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating them. Further, a correlation reflects the strength and direction of the relationship between two (or more) variables Ngag (2023). The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative. Correlational research is ideal for gathering data quickly from natural settings. That helps you generalize your findings to real-life situations in an externally valid way.

Respondents of the Study

This study's respondents were the college students majoring in mathematics at Senator Ninoy Aquino College Foundation school year 2023-2024.

Respondents	Population	Sample	Total
College Students Majoring in Mathematics	36	36	36

Sampling Techniques

This study's respondents were selected using total enumeration techniques to gather data on Reading Comprehension Skills and Word Problem Performance of BSED-mathematics Major in Senator Ninoy Aquino College Foundation at Senator Ninoy Aquino Sultan Kudarat school year 2023-2024.

This research used the total enumeration sampling technique. According to Sugiyono, (2014), total enumeration technique is a sampling technique where the whole members of population that have a particular set of characteristics are treated as sample.

Also Bantillo, and Ngag, (2024) stressed that total enumeration sampling technique is used when the population members are small.

Research Instruments

This study employed a researcher-made survey questionnaire to level the reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of BSED – Mathematics majors. The questionnaire was validated by the professional expert’s in research. According to Ngag (2023), validation of instrument is necessary to gather a scholarly and reliable data for the study.

A Four-Point Likert Scale was also utilized in this study to analyze the survey questionnaire replies of the respondents. The survey questionnaire data will be reviewed and interpreted using the rating scales given below, which are based on the work of numerous researchers:

Four-Point Likert Scale researchers to include four extreme options without a neutral choice, respondents gives an specific and exact replies. Meaning the respondents give a clear reply without being neutral.

The Likert scale was used to evaluate the weighted mean on the level of reading comprehension skills of the BSED-Mathematics major.

RATING	RANGE OF MEANS	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	INTERPRETATION
4	3.25 -4.00	Excellent	Proficient
3	2.50-3.24	Very Good	Strong
2	1.76 – 2.49	Adequate	Satisfactory
1	1– 1.75	Fair	Limited

Another Likert scale patterned after the study of Cerdana, and Ngag, (2024) was used to evaluate the weighted mean on the level of word problem performance of the BSED-Mathematics major.

RATING	RANGE OF MEANS	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	INTERPRETATION
4	3.25 -4.00	Excellent	Outstanding
3	2.50-3.24	Very Good	Strong
2	1.76 – 2.49	Satisfactory	Capable
1	1 – 1.75	Fair	Developing

RATING	RANGE OF MEANS	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	INTERPRETATION
4	3.25-4.00	Very Fast	Excellent
3	2.50-3.24	Fast	Very good
2	1.76-2.49	Moderate	Fair
1	1.00-1.75	Slow	Poor

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure reliable and authentic findings, the researcher adhered to a methodology that aligns with the objectives of the inquiry.

Initially, the study's implementation required the endorsement of the school dean and principal through the affixation of their respective signatures on a formal document.

An additional authorization letter was dispatched to the Senator Ninoy Aquino College Foundation. A survey questionnaire was utilized, developed, and assessed to ensure the accuracy of the data collected for this study. The researcher intends to employ a total of enumeration techniques by utilizing select participants for the study.

Provided that the health protocol was adhered to, the investigator-initiated the dissemination of the Survey Questionnaire in a face-to-face manner. Ultimately, the outcomes derived from the distributed survey questionnaire were compiled, assessed, and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment

Upon the culmination of the study, the collected data was systematically arranged, presented in tabular form, subjected to rigorous analysis, and subsequently interpreted. Consequently, the statistical techniques outlined in Chapter I were utilized to address the aforementioned issues.

Initially, the Mean statistical measure was employed to calculate the proficiency level of reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of BSED-mathematics major at Senator Ninoy Aquino College Foundation at Senator Ninoy Aquino Sultan Kudarat for the academic year 2023-2024.

On the other hand, Pearson's r correlation was employed to calculate the significant relationship between the extent of Reading Comprehension Skills and Word Problem Performance of the BSED-mathematics major.

Scope and Delimitation

The study was limited to determining the reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of the BSED-mathematics major for the school year 2023-2024.

The respondents of this study are college learners taking up Bachelor of Secondary Education Majoring in Mathematics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills

The level of reading comprehension skills of the BSED-Mathematics major in inferential Comprehension obtained a mean of 1.768, which was interpreted as satisfactory, and evaluative Comprehension got a mean of 1.8, which falls under the interpretation as satisfactory. Generally, the summary result of the level of reading comprehension skills of the BSED-mathematics major is 1.784, which is interpreted as satisfactory. The results indicate that the level of reading comprehension of BSED-mathematics students is commendable, it also reveals that BSED Mathematics students can derive meaning from written language, read between the lines, go beyond the literal meaning, and create new meanings and relationships that extend beyond the text's scope. In the study of Murphy and Untiah (2015) suggests that weaker reading comprehension skills may, in part, be responsible for lower levels of academic achievement beyond learners. (Ngag, 2023) stated that weaker reading comprehension skills delay the growth of reading comprehension.

Level of Word Problem Performance

The level of word problem performance of the BSED-Mathematics major in accuracy in problem-solving obtained a mean of 1.788, which is interpreted as capable, and speed in problem-solving got a mean of 1.764, which falls under the interpretation of fair. Generally, the summary result of the level of word problem performance of the BSED-mathematics major garnered a section of 1.776, which is interpreted as capable/fair. The results entail that the level of word problem performance of the BSED-mathematics major is capable and fair, it shows that mathematics students can accurately identify problems and efficiently develop solutions. However, there is a deficiency in speed, students frequently fail to execute solutions swiftly despite possessing adequate conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills. The study of Wickelgren (1977), as cited by Ackerman (2016), who stated that the function describing the relationship is usually clearly non-linear. Accuracy increases rapidly as the speed decreases.

Relationship between the Reading Comprehension Skills and Word Problem Performance of BSED- Mathematics Major

The relationship between the Reading Comprehension Skills and Word Problem Performance of BSED- Mathematics Major as the study reveal the p-values (0.0230 and 0.4981) have less than 0.05 levels of significance, which statistically implies that there is a significant relationship between the independent (x) variable and the dependent (y) variable. Hence, the results of this study show that there is a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and word problem performance in BSED-Mathematics Major. This suggests that among BSED-Mathematics Major students, there is a significant correlation between their ability to understand written texts and their performance in answering mathematical word problems. The results imply that students who are more proficient in reading comprehension also typically do better when it comes to answering mathematical word problems. Boonen et., al. (2013) found that reading comprehension had medium to extensive relation with word problem-solving.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of BSED mathematics are satisfactory in terms of evaluative Comprehension and inferential Comprehension.

It has also been drawn that the reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of BSED mathematics in terms of accuracy and speed in problem-solving are capable or fair.

Finally, reading comprehension skills and word problem performance of the BSED-mathematics students have a significant relationship where the reading skills affected the word problem performance of mathematics students.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusion of the research study, the following are recommended:

1. SNACF administrators may provide more supplementary materials in the form of books and other reading materials that can help students enhance their reading comprehension.
2. SNACF administrators' may organize seminars and workshops to enhance the reading comprehension of the students.
3. The teacher may implement regular problem-solving and incorporate real-word problem-solving task in mathematics subjects that can help students enhance their reading comprehension, logical inferences and encourage students to justify their answer with supporting evidence.
4. The students are encouraged to spend time on reading and self-practice problem-

solving tasks.

5. The future researchers may conduct study to further analyze the effect of Reading Comprehension in the mathematical skills of students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that they complied with obtaining informed consent, the respondents were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgements

The researchers would like to express their sincere gratitude to the following individuals and organization for their invaluable support and assistance in the completion for this study;

The Almighty and Heavenly Father our Savior and Protector, thank you for wisdom and for your guidance throughout our research work to complete successfully;

Lynn P. Belnas, MAT, President, for approval of this study and providing invaluable guidance throughout this research;

Lemuel Colis, academic teacher and also a researcher's panel, for imparting his knowledge and expertise in this study.

Iries J. Ilisan, adviser who heartedly giving a nonstop support and efforts throughout this research, for her patience, advice and guidance to lead the researchers in the path they should take;

Ma. Fe P. Sinadjan, principal, for giving the researcher's opportunity to do and pursue this study;

Parents, who have continuously giving a moral support and financially support to accomplish this research;

BSED-MATHEMATICS major students of Senator Ninoy Aquino College Foundation, for the active participation during the conduct of this study.

REFERENCES

- Ackerman P. (2016). Speed and accuracy indicators of test performance under different instructional condition: Intelligence correlates (pp. 1-9) and R&D Approaches.
- Bantillo, R. B., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). CHANGING LANDSCAPE OF FILIPINO EDUCATION: TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES ON TRADITIONAL VS. MODERNIZED APPROACHES TO TEACHING FILIPINO. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(6), 2409–2420. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12635314>
- Bhandari, P. (2021). *An Introduction to Correlational Research*.

- Boonen et al. (2013). What underlies successful word problem solving? A path analysis in sixth grade students *Contemporary Educational Psychology* 38(3):271–279
- Cerdana, CC, & Ngag, JBJU (2024). IMPLEMENTATION OF TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION (TLE) PROGRAM IN TACURONG CITY DIVISION: ITS IMPACT ON THE HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' CAREER PREPAREDNESS. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2 (8), 735–746. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13292709>
- Costas, G. C. (2022). Reading Comprehension Skills and Numeracy Performance of Grade 8 Students.
- Murphy P., & Unthiah, A., (2015). A Systematic review of intervention research examining English language and literacy development in children with English as an Additional Language (EAL) 2/67.
- Ngag, J.B. (2023). Unveiling The Literary Appreciation of Teduray Students: A Case Study Analysis of Their Works. *Boletin De Literatura Oral - Tradition Oral Literature*, 10(1), 30-3. <http://boletindeliteratuoral.com/index.php/bdlo/article/view/5>
- Ngag, J.B. (2023). Efficacy of Téduray Literature Module in Teaching English. *CEMJP*, 31(1), 404–409. <https://doi.org/10.57030/23364890.cemj.31.1.3>
- Nicolas, C. A. T., & Emata, C. Y. (2018). An integrative approach through reading comprehension to enhance problem-solving skills of grade 7 mathematics students. *International Journal of Innovation in Science and Mathematics Education*, 26(3).
- Ronquillo, K. C., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). OVERCOMING LINGUISTIC HURDLES: INVESTIGATING CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY MAGUINDANAON STUDENTS IN ACHIEVING PROFICIENCY IN SPEAKING ENGLISH. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 1069–1081. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13133747>
- Sugiyono, A. (2014) *Educational Research Methods Quantitative, Qualitative,*
- Vilenius, T P. M., Aunola, K., & Nurmi, J. E. (2008). The association between mathematical word problems and reading comprehension. *Educational Psychology*, 28(4), 409-426.